

ANALYZING THE IMPACTS OF OPEN DATA PORTALS ON URBAN DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATIONS IN GERMAN CITIES

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1. Introduction

In the last ten years, thanks to technological innovations, there has been a fundamental change in urban planning and governance. The availability of data sets, IT solutions or online dashboards has enabled cities to use them for efficient public services, thereby also improving the quality of life in cities. One of the most important approaches here is the use of open data. Open data is seen as central to enabling other services and innovations for society in addition to improving processes within public administration (Horáková 2017; Linåker, Runeson 2020). Open data portals play a major role here (Publications Office of the European Union 2022). However, the increasing opportunities for urban development also raise questions regarding implementation at the municipal level.

The aim of the article is to use the example of Berlin and Dresden to learn more about the functionality of open data portals from the user's perspective and to present the barriers and pathfinders for the accessibility, usability and impact of open data portals at the municipal level. From the point of view of spatial planning and urban development, the advantages for public participation, transparency of administrative actions and fair urban development should be worked out. The central research questions in this regard are a) How do different stakeholders use open data portals in the city of Berlin and Dresden? and b) How effective are they for data-driven planning and decision-making?

The use of open data for planning and communication between city politics, administration, citizens and civil society is the focus of this study. According to Tim-Berners Lee 5-Star model, cities have the opportunity to increasingly use this data for spatial planning, especially in the areas of land use, housing, traffic, infrastructure, environment and Communication. Key reasons for using open data for spatial planning and development are:

a) Transparency - in order to democratize planning procedures and monitor administrative action. To achieve this, it is important that citizens and other stakeholders not only have easy access to the data, but can also use it freely and effectively.

b) social and economic added value - for any dataset such as geospatial, traffic, health or environmental data, there may be a number of other purposes beyond what was initially envisaged. The creative freedom to innovate with these data sets makes it possible to better exploit their social and economic value.

c) Participatory governance - because through open data initiatives, citizens do not remain passive "recipients" of urban development, but can get involved as active stakeholders. The cooperation between citizens and administration is better structured and more regular, which improves participation in the cities (Attard et al., 2015).

2. Methodology

For this study, Berlin and Dresden was used as a case study as it has been pursuing an open data strategy since 2011 and 2016 respectively. Both the open data portals in both cities have a comprehensive range of multi-format data sets and a wide range of applications. In addition, there is strict coordination of the provision of open data within the administration.

In order to analyze the availability and impact of these two open data portals on urban development, twelve expert interviews were conducted in Berlin's open data ecosystem and ten expert interviews in Dresden. The selected experts hold important positions and have published studies, some on open data. All interviews were held between April and August 2022, and included representatives from urban planning, IT, data science, the Senate, business, research and civil society. During the interviews, respondents were asked qualitative questions about the accessibility and usability of open data portals and their impact on urban development, planning, governance and aspects of city management. The interviews were recorded and then transcribed.

Comparable methods of content analysis and frameworks by (Kuckartz and Rädiker 2022; Máchová et al. 2018; Norton, 2008) were used to derive a user-centered evaluation approach with the help of content analysis. The transcripts were coded to derive categories that can be used to identify key barriers and enablers. Through the interviews, we classified barriers and enablers in terms of a) accessibility – the ease of finding relevant datasets, b) usability – the quality and interoperability of the datasets, and c) impact – the desired outcomes and improvements for urban development (Nikiforova, 2022).

3. Results and Way Forward

Berlin and Dresden are at different open-data maturity levels, hence barriers and enablers vary: Berlin completes 11 years in its Open Data journey and is developing Open Data Strategy 2.0 with an aim to achieve 5-Star Linked Open Data Model, strengthen data governance and public relations for Civic Tech (Figure 1). Dresden completes 6 years and requires a robust long-term strategy to address the present disintegrated approach, with a further aim to strengthen open data ecosystem promoting its use for urban innovations (Figure 2).

Large Cities (5% of Germany) vs Medium and Small Towns/Cities (95% of Germany): The economic capital, access to technological tools and human resource expertise available to large cities makes them frontrunners to benefit from open data for improved urban planning, provision

of urban services and participatory governance activities. Medium and Small towns/cities face challenges to raise economic resources and human capital to adopt digital tools for urban governance and innovations. Hence, to address this disparity, special emphasis in the form of Open Data Strategy/Policy, annual budgets, human resources, technical expertise and capacity building are required to empower such towns/cities.

Figure 1. Results from Berlin

Figure 2. Results from Dresden

The use of open data in spatial planning is in its initial stages and the trend towards increased adoption of digitization with more updated data sets, including live data and big data, has the potential to become ‘mainstream’ in urban development activities.

References

Attard, J., Orlandi, F., Scerri, S., Auer, S. (2015). A systematic review of open government data initiatives. *Government Information Quarterly* 32(4): 399–418. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2015.07.006>

Both, W., Schieferdecker, I. (Hrsg.) (2012). Executive Summary Berlin Open Data Strategy - Organisational, legal and technical aspects of Open Data in Berlin, Concept, pilot system and recommendations for action.

Bürger, T., Hoch, A., Bertelsmann Stiftung (2020). Open Data in Kommunen: Eine Kommunalbefragung zu Chancen und Herausforderungen der Bereitstellung offener Daten. *Leb. Kommune* 4. <https://doi.org/10.11586/2020068>

Colpaert, P., Joye, S., Mechant, P., Mannens, E., de Walle, R.V. (2013). The 5 stars of open data portals. *Proceedings MeTTeG 2013*(7) 61-67.

- de Juana-Espinosa, S., Luján-Mora, S. (2020). Open government data portals in the European Union: A dataset from 2015 to 2017. *Data Brief* 29: 105156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2020.105156>
- Elixmann, Y., Jarke, J. (2022). Considering the Reluctance to Adopt Open Data in German Public Administration: An Exploration of Individual Innovation-Decisions. *JeDEM - EJournal EDemocracy Open Gov.* 14(1): 50–71. <https://doi.org/10.29379/jedem.v14i1.681>
- Horáková, E. (2017). Open Data Potential in the Realm of Urban Planning, In *PhD Research Symposium 2017. Fakulta architektury VUT v Brne, Brno, Czech republic.* 6–12. <https://doi.org/10.13164/phd.fa2017.1>
- Kuckartz, U., Rädiker, S. (2022). *Qualitative Inhaltsanalyse: Methoden, Praxis, Computerunterstützung: Grundlagentexte Methoden*, 5. Auflage. ed, Grundlagentexte Methoden. Beltz Juventa, Weinheim Basel.
- Linåker, J., Runeson, P. (2020). Collaboration in Open Government Data Ecosystems: Open Cross-sector Sharing and Co-development of Data and Software. 290–303. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-57599-1_22
- Máchová, R., Hub, M., Lnenicka, M. (2018). Usability evaluation of open data portals: Evaluating data discoverability, accessibility, and reusability from a stakeholders' perspective. *Aslib Journal of Information Management* 70(3): 252–268. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AJIM-02-2018-0026>
- Nikiforova, A. (2022). The role of open data in transforming the society to Society 5.0: a resource or a tool for SDG-compliant Smart Living? <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2206.11784>
- Nikiforova, A., Lnenicka, M. (2021). A multi-perspective knowledge-driven approach for analysis of the demand side of the Open Government Data portal. *Government Information Quarterly* 38(4): 101622. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2021.101622>
- Norton, R.K. (2008). Using content analysis to evaluate local master plans and zoning codes. *Land Use Policy* 25: 432–454. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2007.10.006>
- Open Knowledge Foundation (2022). What is open? Open Data. Available at <https://okfn.org/opendata/>. Accessed August 30, 2022.
- Publications Office of the European Union. 2022. Open data maturity report 2021. Publications Office, LU.